

Numerical solution of fractional pantograph differential equations via Lucas polynomials

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Abstract

The principal purpose of the current work is to solve a class of time-space fractional pantograph differential equations. We present the operational matrices of fractional integral operator and pantograph for Lucas polynomials. Then, these matrices are applied to convert the considered problem to a system of algebraic equations with unknown coefficients. Then, two examples are presented to demonstrate the effectiveness of the present method.

Keywords: Numerical method, Pantograph differential equations, Lucas polynomial, Operational matrix
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1 Introduction

Time-delay systems have been studied in the last few decades. It has shown to fit many problems in different fields, such as economics, biology, physiology, chemistry, physics, mechanics, engineering, etc [1]. One of the most important types of these equations is the fractional pantograph differential equation.

1.1 Lucas polynomials and some fundamental relations

Lucas polynomials are given by the following relation [2]

$$L_0(x) = 2, \quad L_m(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \frac{m}{m-j} \binom{m-j}{j} x^{m-2j} \quad (m \geq 1). \quad (1)$$

1.2 The fractional integral operator operational matrix

The Riemann–Liouville fractional integration matrix of the vector $L(x)$, can be obtained $I^\nu L(x) \simeq P^\nu L(x)$, where P^ν is the $(n+1) \times (n+1)$. Using Eq. (1) and the properties of the operator I^ν , for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n$, we have

$$I^\nu L_i(x) = I^\nu \left(\sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i}{i-r} x^{(i-2r)} \right) = \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i}{i-r} I^\nu \left(x^{(i-2r)} \right)$$

giving consideration to the characteristics of the Riemann–Liouville integration, we have:

$$I^\nu L_i(x) \simeq \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} b_{i,r} x^{(i-2r)+\nu}, \quad b_{i,r} = \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i}{i-r} \frac{\Gamma(i-2r+1)}{\Gamma(i-2r+\nu+1)}.$$

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We can expand $x^{(i-2r)+\nu}$ in terms of Lucas polynomials as $x^{(i-2r)+\nu} \simeq \sum_{j=0}^n c_{rj} L_j(x)$. Then, we get

$$I^\nu L_i(x) \simeq \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} b_{i,r} \sum_{j=0}^n c_{r,j} L_j(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n \left(\sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} b_{i,r} c_{r,j} \right) L_j(x).$$

Now, let $\theta_{i,j,r} = \sum_{j=0}^n b_{i,r} c_{r,j}$. We obtain

$$I^\nu L_i(x) \simeq \underbrace{\left[\sum_{r=0}^n \theta_{i,0,r}, \sum_{r=0}^n \theta_{i,1,r}, \dots, \sum_{r=0}^n \theta_{i,n,r} \right]}_{P_{i,\nu}} L(x), \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n,$$

and $P^\nu = [P_{i,\nu}]$.

1.3 Pantograph operational matrix

Let

$$L(qx) = D_q L(x), \quad 0 < q < 1, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad (2)$$

where the matrix D_q is the pantograph operational matrix of Lucas polynomials. For $i=0$, we have $L_0(qx) = L_0(x) = 2$, which can be written as $L_0(qx) = [2, 0, 0, \dots, 0]L(x)$. By considering Eq. (2) for $i \geq 1$,

$$L_i(qx) = \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i}{i-r} (qx)^{(i-2r)} = \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i}{i-r} q^{(i-2r)} x^{(i-2r)} = \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \varphi_{i,r} x^{(i-2r)},$$

where $\varphi_{i,r} = \binom{i-r}{r} \frac{i}{i-r} q^{(i-2r)}$. Now, we extend x^{i-2r} utilizing Lucas polynomials. Then, we get

$$L_j(qx) \simeq \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \varphi_{i,r} \sum_{j=0}^n c_{r,j} L_j(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n \left(\sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \varphi_{i,r} c_{r,j} \right) L_j(x).$$

Let $\sigma_{i,j,r} = \varphi_{i,r} c_{r,j}$, we have

$$L_i(qx) \simeq \left[\sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \sigma_{i,0,r}, \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \sigma_{i,1,r}, \dots, \sum_{r=0}^{\lfloor i/2 \rfloor} \sigma_{i,n,r} \right] L(x).$$

2 Main results

In this section, the application of the scheme is discussed for solving the following problem:

$$D^\nu u(x) = a(x)u(x) + \sum_{r=1}^l b_r(x) D^\nu u(q_r x), \quad x \in [0, 1], \quad n-1 < \nu \leq n, \quad (3)$$

where, $u^{(i)}(0) = \mu_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$. We consider the expansion of $D^\nu u(x)$ by the Lucas polynomials as

$$D^\nu u(x) \simeq C^T L(x). \quad (4)$$

By using Caputo derivative properties and operational matrices, we have

$$u(x) = I^\nu (C^T L(x)) + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\mu_i}{i!} x^i \simeq C^T P^\nu L(x) + \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\mu_i}{i!} x^i \simeq C^T P^\nu L(x) + E^T L(x). \quad (5)$$

By inserting Eqs. (2), (4) and (5) in Eq. (3), and by applying the collocation method at $x_i = \frac{i}{n}, i = 0, 1, \dots, n$, the considered problem convert to a system of algebraic equations, which can be solved using "FindRoot" package in Mathematica software.

Figure 1: $u(x)$ for $n = 5$, $\nu = 1$ with $\nu = 0.65, 0.75, 0.85, 0.95, 1$, and the exact solution for Example 3.2.

3 Numerical examples

Example 3.1. Consider the following fractional pantograph differential equation

$$D^\nu u(x) = \frac{3}{4}u(x) + u\left(\frac{1}{2}x\right) - x^2 + 2, \quad 1 < \nu \leq 2,$$

where, $u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 0$. The analytic solution of this example for $\nu = 2$ is $u(x) = x^2$. By employing the present method for $n = 2$, the exact solution is obtained.

Example 3.2. Consider the following fractional pantograph differential equation

$$D^\nu u(x) = -u(x) + \frac{1}{10}u\left(\frac{2}{10}x\right) - \frac{1}{10}e^{-\frac{2}{10}x}, \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

where, $u(0) = 1$. The exact solution of this problem is $u(x) = e^{-x}$, when $\nu = 1$. We apply the present method for $n = 5$, in $\nu = 1$. In Table 1, the absolute errors of the present method are shown. It compares our results with those reported by collocation method in [3]. Moreover, Figure 1 displays the approximate solutions for some values of ν .

Table 1: The absolute errors for $\nu = 1$ in Example 3.2

x	Method in [3]	Present method (n=5)
2^{-2}	1.08×10^{-5}	3.05×10^{-7}
2^{-3}	3.81×10^{-5}	2.39×10^{-7}
2^{-4}	1.26×10^{-5}	3.25×10^{-7}
2^{-5}	4.09×10^{-5}	3.47×10^{-8}
2^{-6}	1.20×10^{-5}	3.97×10^{-7}

Conclusion

In this paper, an efficient method for solving a class of fractional pantograph differential equations is proposed. The operational matrices of integral operator and pantograph are introduced for Lucas polynomials. The scheme is developed by these operational matrices and collocation method. The numerical examples display that the method is more accurate and efficient than some existing methods.

References

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